

First records of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) for Serbia

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ABSTRACT: The first records of the Nearctic assassin bug species *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae: Harpactorini) for Serbia are reported. The spread of the species in the Mediterranean Region is summarised and discussed.

KEYWORDS: *Zelus renardii*, invasive species, first records, distribution, Serbia, Mediterranean Region.

The Nearctic leafhopper assassin bug *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae: Harpactorini) is an invasive species with an exceptional spreading ability. In less than 15 years after the first European records of the species in Greece (Davranoglou, 2011; Petrakis & Moullet, 2011) and in Spain (Baena & Torres, 2012; Vivas, 2012), *Z. renardii* established stable populations in various countries of the Mediterranean Region (Kment & van der Heyden, 2022; van der Heyden, 2022, 2023; John & Kolokotronis, 2023; Kulijer et al., 2024; iNaturalist, 2025).

Herein, the first records of *Z. renardii* in Serbia are reported: On 19.09.2024 and on 11.07.2025, two adult specimens were found in Duvanište, a district of the city of Niš, located in the south-eastern part of the country. Photos of both specimens and related data were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist by a user with the pseudonym sanca13 (2024, 2025).

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These recent records from Serbia confirm the ongoing spread of *Z. renardii* in the Mediterranean Region (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 in the Mediterranean Region. (Map created using iNaturalist (2025)).

REFERENCES

- Baena, M., Torres, J.L., 2012, Nuevos datos sobre heterópteros exóticos en España y Francia: *Tempyra biguttula* Stål, 1874, *Belonochilus numenius* (Say, 1832) y *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1856) (Heteroptera: Rhyparochromidae, Orsillidae, Reduviidae), *Boletín de la Asociación Española de Entomología*, 36 (3-4): 351-360.
- Davranoglou, L.R., 2011, *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1856), a New World reduviid discovered in Europe (Hemiptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae), *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*, 147: 157-162.
- iNaturalist, 2025, [Online database], Leafhopper Assassin Bug. Available from: https://www.inaturalist.org/observations?neat=47.02093713158399&nelng=39.497749999999998&subview=map&swlat=29.09461697868098&swlng=-11.766850950000007&taxon_id=244407. (Accessed: 12.07.2025).
- John, E., Kolokotronis, D., 2023, First record of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) for Cyprus, *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*, 159: 59-65.
- Kment, P., van der Heyden, T., 2022, *Zelus renardii* (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae): first records from Croatia, Montenegro, and an accidental introduction to the Czech Republic, *Heteroptera Poloniae – Acta Faunistica*, 16: 7-14.
- Kulijer, D., Dender, D., Martinović, M., 2024, *Zelus renardii* (Hemiptera: Reduviidae), the first record for Bosnia and Herzegovina and the earliest occurrence in Croatia, *Entomologia Croatica*, 22 (1) (2023): 21-26.
- Petrakis, P.V., Moulet, P., 2011, First record of the Nearctic *Zelus renardii* (Heteroptera, Reduviidae, Harpactorinae) in Europe, *Entomologia Hellenica*, 20: 75-81.
- sanca13, 2024, Nordamerikanische Zikaden-Raubwanze (*Zelus renardii*). Photograph to be found on iNaturalist [Online database]. Available from: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/242704014>. (Accessed: 12.07.2025).
- sanca13, 2025, Nordamerikanische Zikaden-Raubwanze (*Zelus renardii*). Photograph to be found on iNaturalist [Online database]. Available from: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/297137950>. (Accessed: 12.07.2025).

- van der Heyden, T., 2022, First record of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae) in Bulgaria, *Journal of the Heteroptera of Turkey*, 4 (2): 139-140.
- van der Heyden, T., 2023, On the presence of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) in Algeria, *Heteroptera Poloniae – Acta Faunistica*, 17: 99-100.
- Vivas, L., 2012, Primera cita en España de la especie *Zelus renardii* (Kolenati, 1857) (Heteroptera: Reduviidae) que representa la segunda cita en Europa, *BV news Publicaciones Científicas*, 1 (6): 34-40.